

In-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular IMplantable devices

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Lead beneficiary	UCL
Author(s)	Silvia Schievano (UCL), Claudio Capelli (UCL), Jan Brüning (CHA), Raphaëlle Lesage (VPH), Christian Ohmann (ECRIN), Maria Panagiotopoulou (ECRIN), Ebba Montgomery Liljeroth (UCL), Bernard Staumont (VPHi).
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Executive summary

This document was developed to provide a *standard operating procedure* (SOP) on clinical (secondary use) and preclinical in vivo data acquisition in order to create virtual cohorts for in-silico modelling. Considering the different requirements and processes involved in the acquisition of clinical vs. preclinical data, the document is split into 2 parts. Additionally, the SOP is designed for SIMCor partners as well as for the overall scientific community. Different countries and local organisations follow several different regulations and procedures for the acquisition and processing of data for research purposes. Therefore, this SOP provides general recommendations and comments, along with specific examples related to the SIMCor use cases: *transcatheter aortic valve implantation* (TAVI) for clinical data acquired at *University College London* (UCL) and *Charité* (CHA), and *pulmonary artery pressure sensors* (PAPS) for preclinical data acquisition.

Table of contents

INTRODUCTION	4
SOP ON CLINICAL DATA ACQUISITION FOR IN-SILICO MODELS (SOP-SIMCOR_4.1.1)	5
COVER PAGE OF THE SOP	5
PURPOSE	6
SCOPE	6
DEFINITIONS	6
PROCEDURE.....	8
1. <i>Identify population</i>	8
2. <i>Identify data for the modelling purpose</i>	9
3. <i>Evaluate research governance, data protection policies and data management plan</i>	11
4. <i>Data extraction and storage</i>	13
CONTINGENCIES	15
PUBLICATION POLICY	15
REFERENCES	15
SOP ON PRECLINICAL IN-VIVO DATA ACQUISITION FOR IN-SILICO MODELS (SOP-SIMCOR_4.1.2)	16
COVER PAGE OF THE SOP	16
PURPOSE	17
SCOPE	17
PROCEDURE.....	17
1. <i>Evaluate applicable regulations and guidelines for preclinical animal studies planning</i>	17
2. <i>Define rationale of animal experimentation</i>	18
3. <i>Justify choice of the animal model</i>	19
4. <i>Animal welfare considerations</i>	20
5. <i>Document responsibilities regarding experiments</i>	21
6. <i>Experimental design and data storage</i>	21
CONTINGENCIES	23
PUBLICATION POLICY	23
REFERENCES	23

List of figures

FIGURE 1: DATA ACQUISITION SCHEMATIC FOR THE GENERATION OF VIRTUAL COHORTS AS DESCRIBED IN THIS SOP.	4
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List of tables

TABLE 1: OVERVIEW OF THE DIFFERENT DATA TYPE CATEGORIES AND THEIR RESPECTIVE ACQUISITION TIME WITH RESPECT TO TAVI DATE, WITH EXAMPLES OF RELEVANT PARAMETERS FOR THE IN-SILICO MODEL AND VIRTUAL COHORT.	10
TABLE 2: OVERVIEW OF THE DIFFERENT DATA TYPE CATEGORIES WITH RESPECT TO THEIR STORAGE LOCATIONS AND DESTINATION FORMAT.	14

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
CHA	Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin
CT	Computed tomography
DMP	Data management plan
ECRIN	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network
EHR	Electronic health record
GDPR	General data protection regulation
NYHA	New York Heart Association
PACS	Picture archiving and communication system
PAPS	Pulmonary artery pressure sensors
SOP	Standard operating procedure
TAVI	Transcatheter aortic valve implantation
UCL	University College of London
VPH	Virtual physiological human

Introduction

This document highlights the different steps and considerations involved in the collection of data required for generation of virtual cohorts for cardiovascular applications, which is the focus of SIMCor. Virtual cohorts can be used for the assessment of cardiovascular medical devices in in-silico trials, aiming at accelerating design improvement and the certification process throughout the product development process. This document is meant to be applicable to a broad range of healthcare in-silico research projects, as illustrated in *Figure 1*, and, where applicable, existing standards for patient inclusion criteria, research governance, data extraction and exchange are referenced. Examples illustrate the specific SIMCor requirements for acquisition of retrospective clinical data for TAVI modelling and of preclinical data for a PAPS use case.

Figure 1: Data acquisition schematic for the generation of virtual cohorts as described in this SOP.

SOP on clinical data acquisition for in-silico models (SOP-SIMCOR_4.1.1)

Cover page of the SOP

SIMCor responsible partner	University College London (UCL)				
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Purpose and field of application

Acquisition of retrospective clinical data (i.e., secondary use) for developing and validating cohorts of virtual patients for numerical predictive models used in the context of medical device design and development.

Contributors

Function	Name and title	Affiliation	Signature and date
Author1	Silvia Schievano, Prof	UCL	
Author2	Jan Brüning, Dr	CHA	
Author3	Raphaëlle Lesage, Dr	VPHi	
Author4	Claudio Capelli, Dr	UCL	
Author5	Ebba Montgomery Liljeroth	UCL	
Author6	Christian Ohmann, Prof.	ECRIN	
Author7	Bernard Staumont, Dr	VPHi	
Author8	Anna Rizzo	LYN	
Reviewer1	Jan Brüning	CHA	
Reviewer2	Prasanna Hariharan	FDA	
Reviewer3	Jan Küfner	TÜV Süd	
Approver1:	Liesbet Geris	VPHi	
Approver2:	PC: Titus Kühne or PM: Edwin Morley-Fletcher	CHA, LYN	

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V1.0	SOP-D4.1.1-RAB	Pre-final version for Regulatory and Clinical advisory boards
V2.0	SOP-D4.1.1-draft	Revised versions pre-delivery
V2.1	SOP-D4.1.1	Deliverable version

Purpose

This part of the SOP applies to the acquisition of retrospective clinical data for developing and validating cohorts of virtual patients for numerical predictive models. As we are dealing with retrospective data, the term acquisition here refers to the process of collecting patient data from hospital secured resources. The data have been acquired previously at the respective clinical centres for the purpose of clinical diagnosis and/or treatment according to their internal, national and international clinical routine protocols. This approach is commonly referred to as secondary use of data from routine medical care. This SOP proposes an acquisition procedure allowing compliance with relevant regulations pertaining to data protection (e.g., GDPR) and ethical guidelines in Europe and in the respective countries, such as the *European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)*¹. While it outlines general steps, details of each step may differ from country to country due to specific national rules and regulations or even clinical centre specific policies and procedures. Hence, we illustrate an exemplary application of the general procedure using the TAVI SIMCor case study, for which data have been acquired in the UK (UCL/Barts) and in Germany at the *Charité - University Hospital Berlin (CHA)*. These specific examples will be highlighted in the main text of the document as follows:

Exemplary use case - specific processing step

This format is used to present practical applications of the general recommendations provided in this manuscript.

Scope

This SOP addresses researchers from different fields (e.g., engineering, mathematics, information technology, medicine) involved in the acquisition and secondary use of clinical data that are required for generation of virtual cohorts. Hence, in the scope of this document the clinical data are assumed to have been primarily acquired during routine clinical procedures and this SOP deals with the acquisition and secondary use of that data for in-silico research purposes, ranging from the definition of the required data to the extraction and storage processes, including legal and data privacy considerations. As this document is rather general, the user requirements or skills for the different steps are strongly heterogeneous depending on the specific use cases. However, researchers must take specific care and appropriate training when personal data are collected as part of the research study, in order to legally comply with local, national and international regulations and standards on data protection.

Definitions

Anonymised data: data that have been stripped of all identifiable information and, therefore, are no longer personal data². GDPR does not apply to such data. According to that regulation, “to determine

¹ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

² Art. 4 GDPR - Definitions <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-4-gdpr/>

whether a natural person is identifiable, account should be taken of all the means reasonably likely to be used, such as singling out, either by the controller or by another person to identify the natural person directly or indirectly. To ascertain whether means are reasonably likely to be used to identify the natural person, account should be taken of all objective factors, such as the costs of and the amount of time required for identification, taking into consideration the available technology at the time of the processing and technological developments”³.

Data controller: natural or legal person who determines the purposes for which and the means by which personal data are processed. The company/organisation that acts as data controller decides ‘why’ and ‘how’ the personal data should be processed. A company/organisation can be a joint controller when, together with one or more organisations, it jointly determines ‘why’ and ‘how’ personal data should be processed. Joint controllers must enter into contract agreements to set out their respective responsibilities.

Data processor: natural or legal person who processes personal data only on behalf of the data controller. The data processor is usually a third party external to the company. However, in the case of groups of undertakings, one undertaking may act as processor for another undertaking. The duties of the processor towards the controller must be specified in a contract or another legal act. For example, the contract must indicate what happens to the personal data once the contract is terminated.

Data life cycle: sequence of stages that the particular unit of data goes through from its initial generation or capture to its eventual destruction process.

Personal data: ‘personal data’ means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person (cited from Art. 4 GDPR - Definitions²).

Primary vs. secondary data: the classification is based on the relationship of the data to the research project purpose. Primary data sources incorporate data collected for direct purposes of the research, typically when the data of interest are not available elsewhere or, if available, are unlikely to be of sufficient accuracy and reliability for the planned analyses and uses. Primary data are prospectively planned and collected under the direction of a protocol or study plan, using common procedures and the same format across different sites and patients. Secondary data sources comprise data originally collected for purposes other than the research project itself, as, for example, standard medical care. Often, secondary data represent the diversity observed in real-world practice and, therefore, may be affected by inconsistencies in collection, measurement, reporting and quality.

Pseudonymised data: data that can no longer be attributed to a specific individual without the use of additional information (key), that is kept separately and is subject to measures to ensure that the data cannot be attributed to the individual². Pseudonymised data are still considered to be personal data as re-identification is possible.

Virtual cohort: a “set of virtual patients that mimics a real patient or subject cohort with respect to all reasonably expected patient states, patient dynamics and evolution of patient condition which might

³ Recital 26 - Not Applicable to Anonymous Data; <https://gdpr-info.eu/recitals/no-26/>

occur in practice”⁴. Each member of the cohort is a physiological model, characterised by its own parameter set, that can predict the same endpoint that would be observed in clinical practice. Moreover, the variation between members represents the real population’s variability⁵.

Procedure

The data life cycle in this SOP starts with the collection of patient data from the hospital secured resources, as explained above. After having well framed the purpose of the data acquisition (e.g., to calibrate the model, validate it, etc.), the first step requires identifying the population of patients fit for purpose, and checking, at a high level, the availability of the required data in the systems, without accessing them yet. Research governance and legal requirements must be evaluated, before starting the actual data collection process. Once all approvals are in place, including anonymisation or pseudonymisation processes, the clinical data can be extracted and transferred for further processing. Storage and archiving are the final steps to close the cycle before the data can be processed, for instance for virtual cohort generation (c.f. SOP D4.2⁶).

1. Identify population

The population of patients (age, gender, pathology, etc.) that should be represented in the dataset to achieve the proposed modelling goals must be identified and described and must match the model context of use. In other words, the inclusion/exclusion criteria should be described and justified, accounting for the availability of the data. Importantly, no personal data is accessed at this stage since no ethical clearance and nor approval was granted yet⁷. Merely, this is an exploration phase for modellers to target the right dataset. The clinical guidelines and internal protocols adopted by individual healthcare centres for delivery of clinical care are key to guarantee the accuracy and trustworthiness of the primary data. They may also allow modellers to get an understanding of the typical data acquired in the clinical routine and hence of possible population characteristics. These guidelines and protocols are often updated; thus, particular attention needs to be taken in the definition of the selected patient populations and acquired secondary data.

TAVI - Identify required population

In the SIMCor example, the overall aim is to create an *in-silico* platform for TAVI device development. Thus, the selection of data for this case study is driven by the requirements to create a virtual cohort of TAVI patients and develop and validate structural TAVI simulations that replicate clinical outcomes. Secondary data are derived from patients who underwent TAVI for aortic stenosis treatment following *European Society of Cardiology* (ESC) guidelines for indications and clinical protocols. Data are used to set up the simulations, validate the results and further describe and

⁴ J. G. Chase, J. C. Preiser, J. L. Dickson, A. Pironet, Y. S. Chiew, C. G. Pretty, G. M. Shaw, B. Benyo, K. Moeller, S. Safaei, M. Tawhai, P. Hunter, T. Desai, Next-generation, personalised, model-based critical care medicine: A state-of-the art review of in silico virtual patient models, methods, and cohorts, and how to validate them. *Biomed. Eng. Online*. **17** (2018), pp. 1–29

⁵ M. Viceconti, C. Cobelli, T. Haddad, A. Himes, B. Kovatchev, M. Palmer, In silico assessment of biomedical products: The conundrum of rare but not so rare events in two case studies. *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part H J. Eng. Med.* **231**, 455–466 (2017).

⁶ Bruning, Jan, Krüger, Nina, Goubergrits, Leonid, Lesage, Raphaëlle, Huberts, Wouter, & Schievano, Silvia. (2021). SIMCor. Deliverable 4.2: Standard operating procedures for data processing for in-silico models (CHA, M12). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6150520>

⁷ Assessing the Credibility of Computational Modeling and Simulation in Medical Device Submissions. Food & Drug Administration (Dec, 2021). <https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/assessing-credibility-computational-modeling-and-simulation-medical-device-submissions>

stratify the population. Using this stratification, as well as validated models, virtual cohorts can be generated according to the main objectives of SIMCor.

Current clinical indications, referral and treatment decisions for patients with severe aortic stenosis have changed in 2021, with all severe aortic stenosis patients requiring aortic valve treatment now evaluated by a multidisciplinary heart team⁸. The clinical guidelines recommend TAVI as the preferred mode of intervention in patients ≥ 75 years of age, based on evaluation of clinical, anatomical and procedural factors, as well as for additional patient groups < 75 years of age. The heart team recommendations are discussed with the patient, who can then make an informed treatment decision between the option of TAVI or surgical valve replacement.

In addition, for the purpose of this study, the following exclusion criteria are adopted:

- Patients aged ≤ 16 years
- Patients who have objected to their data being used for secondary research purpose
- Patients treated before 2014 (UCL/Barts) or 2018 (CHA)
- Patients with no pre-TAVI CT images

At both clinical centres, identification of the patient collectives adhering to the in- and exclusion criteria is performed in collaboration with the clinical fellows involved in the treatment of these patients. At UCL, the cardiology clinical fellows at the Barts Centre, and at CHA, the cardiac surgeons at the German Heart Institute Berlin and interventional cardiologists at the Charité - Universitätsmedizin (Medizinische Klinik mit Schwerpunkt Kardiologie und Angiologie) are consulted on this regard. After ensuring that a viable retrospective cohort is available, the availability of the specific data elements and parameters required for the respective use cases, such as physics-based modelling of the paravalvular leakage or the generation of synthetic TAVI cohorts, is assessed as well by the SIMCor researchers at the respective centres. Datasets are retrieved according to the steps enlisted in the following paragraphs.

2. Identify data for the modelling purpose

Data required for generating virtual patient cohorts for computational modelling usually involve patient demographics, anatomical and physiological measurements, mostly derived from routine imaging procedures such as echocardiography, magnetic resonance imaging and *computed tomography* (CT), procedural information and clinical outcomes. These data are used to set up realistic simulations, including mechanical properties and boundary conditions.

A set of specific parameters has to be identified. Ideally, this step should be performed together with clinicians as well as the researchers using the data within the project. Thus, available data elements can be compared against the requirements of the respective use cases rapidly. Here, it is important to keep in mind that without ethical and data privacy approval, which will be addressed later in this document, no active analysis of clinical data is possible. However, talking to clinicians about estimations of the amount and type of available data sets as well as the information that is usually acquired during the different procedures is possible at this stage of the exploration of data availability.

⁸ 2021 ESC/EACTS Guidelines for the management of valvular heart disease ESC Clinical Practice Guidelines 28 Aug 2021; <https://academic.oup.com/eurheartj/article/43/7/561/6358470?login=true>

Simply put, whenever data is actively opened or searched for within clinical information systems, it is safe to assume that the appropriate approval procedures should be performed beforehand. There might be exemptions, such as dedicated repositories that provide an overview of available data sets directly.

It is good practice to summarise the typical data types available in the clinical dataset and the relevant parameters that could be extracted from it for the modelling purpose (see example below).

TAVI - Identify required data and available parameters in dataset

Table 1 details the type of data resources used for the TAVI example (list reported in more details in D5.1).

Data category	Time of intervention				Examples of relevant parameters
	Pre	Peri	Post	1yr follow-up	
Demographics		√			TAVI date, age, gender, body mass index, operative risk score, NYHA, frailty score, primary diagnosis, previous history and comorbidities;
Procedural notes		√			TAVI delivery; valve manufacturer; expansion mechanism (self-expandible, balloon); nominal valve prosthesis size; positioning (derived from fluoroscopy images); post procedure peak gradient (doppler ultrasound); post procedure mean gradient (doppler ultrasound); post procedure aortic regurgitation; valve malposition (binary); valve-in-valve (unplanned); apical complication; sternotomy; bail out percutaneous coronary intervention; permanent pacing; tavi related patient-prosthesis-mismatch; stroke (record of events); vascular access complications
Echocardiography report	√		√	√	Valve mean and peak gradient; valve area; valve regurgitation; paravalvular regurgitation; total regurgitation; peak aortic velocity; annular diameter; bicuspid aortic valve occurrence; energy loss index; left ventricle end diastolic diameter and mass index
CT report	√				Valve calcium score; valve calcium volume; calcium in left ventricular outflow tract; location/description of calcium in left ventricular outflow tract; average aortic annulus diameter; aortic annulus area; average sinus of valsalva diameter; sinus of valsalva area; average sinotubular junction diameter; sinotubular junction area; maximum ascending aorta diameter; distance right and left coronary artery.
CT DICOM	√				Best Systole (70%), best diastole (30%), contrast mediastinum
Adverse event				√	All causes of mortality and hospitalisation: myocardial infarction, stroke, bleeding, acute kidney injury, vascular complications, conduction disturbances and arrhythmias, and other TAVI related complications.

Table 1: Overview of the different data type categories and their respective acquisition time with respect to TAVI date, with examples of relevant parameters for the in-silico model and virtual cohort.

3. Evaluate research governance, data protection policies and data management plan

Once the data sources, required parameters and information to be extracted from these data sources, as well as the means for their extraction are identified, legal requirements must be evaluated before starting the actual data collection process. The responsible and lawful reuse of personal medical data, that were already lawfully collected, in research projects is set out in several international and national legislations, and clinical centre-based code of conducts and processes. Thus, despite the varying rules from centre to centre, two general aspects must be taken into account for each research project:

- **Research governance approval:** Acquiring approval by the appropriate ethics board or internal review board is vital for conducting any research on human participants, patients, or their personal data. Even when only retrospective datasets are used (as in the case of SIMCor), meaning that no additional interventions, measurements or experiments are performed on the participants, research governance approval by the appropriate internal and/or external review board is required in most cases. However, the procedures regarding application for governance approval differ between different nations and also local institutions.
- **Data privacy assessment:** Processing of patient-specific data is always subject to data privacy regulations, such as the GDPR⁹, or the UK-GDPR¹⁰, unless the data are only available in an anonymised manner and, therefore, are not considered personal data anymore¹¹. While the GDPR is valid in all countries of the European Union and also in the UK after Brexit, its implementation and reading vary. Individual institutions and clinical centres might have dedicated data privacy offices which must be contacted for project assessment and approval. In contrast to the research governance approval, approval of the data privacy might not be required in every case.

These two aspects cannot be entirely separated from each other. Especially in retrospective data analysis (i.e., secondary use of data), the research project ethical assessment will also address aspects of data privacy, as for example risks of re-identification and whether the intended use of the patient data is justified without explicit consent of the patient. However, often two separate entities are responsible for the ethical and the data privacy assessment. In other cases, the internal review board might be responsible for approval of both aspects of retrospective data usage. All partners of the collaborative modelling project who will handle the data should sign a **binding agreement** that defines the role (i.e., data controller, processor, etc.) and responsibility regarding the processing of the personal data.

TAVI - Evaluate and apply privacy protection and inform consent procedures

In the case of UCL and CHA, two separate entities were responsible for the ethical and the data privacy assessment. A self-assessment of the data privacy regulations relevant to the project was carried out at the beginning of the project and is described in a published deliverable *D3.2 - Data Management Plan (LYN, M6)*¹². The ethical approval procedure has been described in detailed in

⁹ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/>

¹¹ <https://gdpr-info.eu/recitals/no-26/>

¹² <https://zenodo.org/record/5095495>

deliverables *D5.1 - Protocol for clinical data collection (CHA, M3)*¹³ and *D5.7 - Ethical committees approval process reports and documents (UCL, M6)*.

Most clinical centres and research institutes have their own standard operating procedures and guidelines for ethical and data privacy approval. Thus, no general consensus on these aspects can be provided in frames of this document. However, the following aspects of the intended data collection are most likely relevant for the approval procedures and should be considered before application. Furthermore, a *data management plan* (DMP) can help establish a set of rules and processes for handling of the research data during and after the end of the project, establishing what data will be collected, processed and/or generated, which methodology & standards will be applied, whether data will be shared/made open access, and how data will be curated & preserved (including after the end of the project). DMP templates are provided for example by the EU Commission for Horizon 2020 projects, if helpful¹⁴.

How was the data primary acquired / measured? Clinical data are acquired following international and national guidelines, and according to individual centres' standard protocols. These are often updated to reflect new evidence of care improvement. Knowledge and understanding of the accuracy and trustworthiness of the primary data that are going to be used in the computational model, can help demonstrate model credibility. The description of the primary acquisition or measurement should highlight the data relevance for the model's context of use (e.g., to justify the applicability of the validation activities for instance).

Is the data already anonymised or pseudonymised? Data that have been previously anonymised or pseudonymised run the risk of re-identification, and measures should be taken to mitigate that risk. Depending on the nature of the initial data, different procedures apply.

How is the data stored? Identify the clinical information systems where the required datasets are stored and their format. Extracting the required information from unstructured sources such as discharge letters may present different challenges compared to for example image data.

How is the data accessed and transferred? Identify rules and clearances required for accessing the data. As primary data in clinical systems is usually not accessible in an anonymised or pseudonymised manner, only selected personnel with appropriate clearance might be allowed to access the data. Available transfer modalities from the clinical to the research site need to be assessed in terms of technical feasibility (is it necessary to copy manually the data or are there interfaces allowing automatic transfer), and in terms of compliance with regulations in the clinical and research infrastructures.

Which processing steps will be performed? Apart from data collection and transferral, the data processor must document which processing steps will be performed. For example, 'reconstruction of patient-specific anatomies from image data'. Additional processing steps might introduce additional risks to the data subjects' privacy and usually must be documented thoroughly.

¹³ <https://zenodo.org/record/4664563>

¹⁴ Data Management Plan example: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm

Which technical and organisational measures are put in place to protect data privacy and security?

Will the data be anonymised or pseudonymised? If pseudonymisation is used, who has access to the re-identification list? How is physical and digital access to the data regulated? Will the data be encrypted? The data processor must document the de-identification method and explain measures to avoid re-identification (e.g., secure storage of identifying key for pseudonymised data or destruction for anonymised data).

Is informed consent required? A very important question to address, both from the ethical and data privacy perspective, is the requirement of informed consent for the intended use. If prospective acquisition of data is envisaged, even if it is only data that is generated during clinical routine, acquisition of informed consent by the patients is recommended. For purely retrospective data, acquisition of informed consent might neither be possible nor necessary depending on the respective regulations. Two common approaches that allow retrospective use of data are opt-out procedures for clinical routine data (e.g., for UCL it was described in *D1.8 - Ethical and legal clearance preliminary assessment (LYN, M4)*) or national laws that provide a legal basis for processing of routine information for academic research (as it is the case for CHA, in SIMCor). Furthermore, if the retrospective data originates from a clinical study rather than from clinical routine, informed consent might have been acquired during the study ('broad consent'). However, even in this situation, data privacy procedure agreements and research governance approvals are still required.

For future regulatory evaluation of the computational model, it is important to keep track of all above information that monitor the data origin or 'data pedigree', to be able to briefly describe the origin of the data included in the model and in-silico analysis. Both European and American agencies align on that matter for computational studies^{15 16}, see *D4.4 - Guidelines for documentation (IIB, M12)*¹⁷ for more details on reporting.

4. Data extraction and storage

Clinical institutions use different systems to store patient data, mostly an *electronic health record* (EHR) and a *picture archiving and communication system* (PACS) for medical images. Assessment and retrieval of the clinical data from the hospital systems to a format usable for research projects are usually done manually, as no sufficient interfaces allowing automated export are available yet.

Data extraction and storage is strongly dependent on national and institutional policies. Ideally, data extraction should be performed in an automated manner to avoid errors introduced due to transferring information from clinical information systems to the data set format used for research. However, this requires a standardised application programming interface as well as availability of data in a structured way, such as a database or spreadsheet (e.g., excel or csv files). Both are not standard in clinical environments. For example, many relevant parameters and values from clinical routine can only be accessed from unstructured data elements, such as surgical or diagnostic reports and referral letters. In those cases, data extraction most likely must be performed by manual transferral of the required data elements.

¹⁵ Reporting the results of population pharmacokinetic analyses https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/scientific-guideline/guideline-reporting-results-population-pharmacokinetic-analyses_en.pdf

¹⁶ Musuamba et al. Scientific and regulatory evaluation of mechanistic in silico drug and disease models in drug development: Building model credibility. CPT: Pharmacometrics & Systems Pharmacology. doi: 10.1002/psp4.12669

¹⁷ Stiehm, Michael, Brüning, Jan, Lesage, Raphaëlle, Cypionka, Thomas, Oldenburg, Jan, Huberts, Wouter, Rolf-Pissarczyk, Malte, Luther; Torsten, Staumont, Bernard, & Geris, Liesbet. (2021). SIMCor. Deliverable 4.4: Guidelines for documentation (IIB, M12). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6150905>

Before data sharing is initiated, de-identification must be considered, removing possible identifiers to minimise the risk of re-identification¹⁸. Data should always be stored at least in a pseudonymised manner, meaning that direct identifiers, such as the name and surname, and quasi-identifiers, such as address, zip code and other sensitive information, are either removed early on or not collected at all, to increase privacy. The international standard ISO/TS 25237:2008¹⁹ defines the basic concepts and provides a methodology to ensure pseudonymisation is qualitatively and lawfully applied. Of course, there might be processing steps that require this information or even re-identification of specific patients. But even in those cases, this information should be stored in a separate document linking the patients to their respective pseudonyms. Access to this re-identification key should be limited. Overall, processing steps must adhere to the descriptions elaborated during the data privacy impact assessment, evaluating the following:

- data privacy and security: the de-identification and any processing to extract parameters should be performed before the data are extracted from the secured storage space.
- re-identification risks and organise management of that risk
- data extraction method: e.g., will a software for segmentation be used to extract geometries?
- data interoperability when datasets are used across systems or enterprises; the data must be rendered interoperable (read accurately by different systems), without loss of privacy protections.

TAVI - Data management plan: Evaluate storage mode

Table 2 demonstrates the location for the TAVI data type categories. Even though most information is stored in a digital manner in either EPR or PACS, transferral of data from these systems to the destination file types requires intensive manual interaction, both at UCL and CHA. For SIMCor, the parameters are first collected and aggregated locally on hospital servers, where they are pseudonymised according to each institution's regulations before being transferred to the research computing environment. Thus, only pseudonymous data are exported to the research computing server and shared with collaborators for further model development and validation.

Data Category	Data storage location	
	Source	Destination
Demographics	EHR	Spreadsheet
Procedural Notes	EHR	Spreadsheet
Echocardiography report	EHR	Spreadsheet
CT report	EHR	Spreadsheet
CT DICOM	PACS	Disk for transfer to image processing software
Adverse Event	EHR	Spreadsheet

Table 2: Overview of the different data type categories with respect to their storage locations and destination format.

Once the data have been retrieved by applying the aforementioned steps, precautions and recommendations, they are ready to be processed for modelling purposes. For that matter, see SIMCOR-SOP-D4.2 on data processing for creating virtual cohorts for in-silico models²⁰.

¹⁸ <https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/7/12/e018647.long>

¹⁹ ISO/TS 25237:2008# on Health informatics — Pseudonymization. <https://www.iso.org/standard/42807.html>

²⁰ <https://zenodo.org/record/6150520>

Contingencies

If the researcher cannot adhere to the content of these SOP instructions for justified reasons, then deviation from the procedure must be documented and appropriate actions must be taken, considering SOP revision if relevant.

Publication policy

The procedure comes from the SIMCor project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017578.

When using the current SOP please acknowledge the SIMCor project by citing: "Schievano, Silvia et al. (2022). SIMCor. Deliverable 4.1: SOP on data preclinical and clinical data acquisition (UCL, M18). Zenodo. [insert link]"

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- General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR. <https://gdpr-info.eu/>
- Guide to the UK General Data Protection Regulation (UK GDPR). <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/>

SOP on preclinical in-vivo data acquisition for in-silico models (SOP-SIMCOR_4.1.2)

Cover page of the SOP

SIMCor responsible partner	Charité (CHA)				
Short Title, ID	SOP-SIMCOR-D4.1.2	Page	1	of	10
Title	SOP for preclinical data acquisition for in-silico models				
Version	2.1	Created on	27/05/2022		
Status	Pre-print	Related SOP	SOP-SIMCOR-D4.2 (data processing) SOP-SIMCOR 4.1.1		

Purpose and field of application

Primary acquisition of preclinical in-vivo (animal) data for developing and validating numerical predictive models used in the context of medical device design and development. The steps are applicable for gathering data for in-silico models in any biomedical field, although they were developed based on requirements for the cardiovascular field as illustrated by the exemplary use case.

Contributors

Function	Name and title	Affiliation	Signature and date
Author1	Jan Brüning, Dr	CHA	
Author2	Raphaëlle Lesage, Dr	VPHi	
Author3	Silvia Schievano, Prof	UCL	
Author4	Bernard Staumont	VPHi	
Author5	Anna Rizzo	LYN	
Reviewer1	TBD	CHA	
Approver1:	Liesbet Geris	VPHi	
Approver2:	PC: Titus Kühne or PM: Edwin Morley-Fletcher	CHA, LYN	

Revision history

Version	Amendment ID	Version summary
V1.0	SOP-D4.1.2-RAB	Pre-final version for Regulatory and Clinical advisory boards
V2.0	SOP-D4.1.2-draft	Revised versions pre-delivery
V2.1	SOP-D4.1.2	Deliverable version

Purpose

Developing and validating numerical predictive models for (cardiovascular) medical device design and development require data. For ethical, economical and practical reasons, and in line with FAIR principles²¹, using retrospective data is the best option, but the required and relevant data may not always be available or accessible for the modelling purpose and context of use. Therefore, acquisition of new data becomes necessary. Unless the biomedical application or question of interest specifically targets animals, the use of human data should always be preferred. However, in some cases, using preclinical animal data is actually relevant for the research question. The purpose of the current procedure is to guide modellers in the acquisition of preclinical animal data following best and lawful practice.

Scope

Applies to the acquisition of prospective preclinical data for developing and validating numerical predictive models. While it outlines general steps, details of each step may differ from country to country due to specific national standards and policies, especially regarding the ethical considerations. Here, we illustrate the procedure with the PAPS use case, developed in SIMCor.

- Data acquisition in view of determining numerical model input parameters
- Data acquisition in view of validating the model.

Procedure

The procedure presented in this document follows these steps necessary to acquire preclinical data: awareness and understanding of the relevant regulations regarding animal experiments; demonstration of the necessity for animal experiments; justification of the chosen animal model and final experimental design. However, these processes might be of iterative nature, requiring recurrent adaptation.

1. Evaluate applicable regulations and guidelines for preclinical animal studies planning

The first step consists in identifying all the relevant European and national laws and guidelines that apply to the planned animal data acquisition. The applicable regulations may differ from country to country; hence researchers must perform a self-evaluation tailored for their project.

Within the European Union, animal experiments are regulated via the directive 2010/63/EU. However, EU directives are implemented via national legislation which allow deviations as long as they are viable to reach the goal of the directive²². Thus, the national legislation is binding for planning, approval and conduction of animal experiments. However, the directive provides a common basis allowing standardisation of regulation of animal experiments in all member states.

Another relevant concept for animal experiments are the so-called **Three Rs**: Replacement, Refinement, Reduction. This principle was initially defined in 1959 by William Russel and Rex Burch²³

²¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

²² e.g., paragraph 7: "Attitudes towards animals also depend on national perceptions, and there is a demand in certain Member States to maintain more extensive animal-welfare rules than those agreed upon at the level of the Union."

²³ <https://caat.jhsph.edu/principles/the-principles-of-humane-experimental-technique>

and is not specific to the EU or its member states, but motivated several aspects of the above-mentioned directive. Furthermore, additional guidelines, such as the 'Guideline on the principles of regulatory acceptance of 3Rs testing approaches'²⁴ by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) exist. Briefly, the 3Rs principle aims at either omitting animal experiments altogether (replacement), or if this is not viable, reduce the number of animals used for the experiments to the absolute minimum (reduction) and keep the animal suffering as minimal as possible. While the 3Rs principle suffers from ambiguity and stakeholder-dependent interpretation²⁵ it is considered in current legislation as the directive 2010/63/EU; animal experiment facilities might have their own SOPs focussing on different aspects of this principle and different initiatives on the national or institutional level aim to promote these principles^{26, 27}.

Smith et al. developed the PREPARE (*Planning Research & Experimental Procedures on Animal: Recommendation for Excellence*) checklist and guideline, which provides guidance for all necessary steps of animal experiments. In addition to the implementation of the 3Rs principle, PREPARE also aims to improve reproducibility of animal research by further standardization. A continuously maintained online representation offering additional information and help for usage of the PREPARE checklist is made available via the Norecopa is *Norway's National Consensus Platform for the advancement of "the 3 Rs" in connection with animal experiments*²⁸. Adhering to this checklist might even be mandatory for publication of animal experiment results in some academic journals.

2. Define rationale of animal experimentation

To justify animal experiments, the device or model to be investigated, must be addressing a relevant need that outweighs the burden of the animals. In addition to that, following the 3R principles mentioned above, animal experiments must only be performed when there are no viable alternatives (reduce principle). Ideally, investigations can be carried out using in-vitro experiments or retrospective data, either from humans or animals (reuse principle), can be utilised. The lack of viable alternatives must be thoroughly described to justify the necessity of animal experiments.

At this point, already a sound understanding of which investigations are to be performed using animal experiments and which data to be collected. From these considerations, a suitable animal model can be chosen in the next steps, allowing refinement of the experimental design. While these steps are described in a consecutive manner in this document, several iterations might be necessary, as competing interests, such as the costs of the experiments, the burden the experiments impose on the animals, and the constraints imposed by the chosen model must all be weighed against each other.

Most likely, justification of animal experiments for the sole purpose of validation of a numerical model will be difficult with respect to the approval by the regulatory bodies. Here, previous investigations using either retrospective data, if viable, or in-vitro experiments should be meticulously explained to demonstrate that progression towards real-world application of the model can only be achieved via animal testing. Furthermore, the model to be investigated must be capable of providing a relevant socio-economic benefit. A mitigation strategy might be to cooperate with existing animal testing

²⁴https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/scientific-guideline/guideline-principles-regulatory-acceptance-3rs-replacement-reduction-refinement-testing-approaches_en.pdf

²⁵ https://proceedings.altex.org/data/2012-01/333336_Olsson31.pdf

²⁶ UK/UCL: <https://www.nc3rs.org.uk/>

²⁷ <https://charite3r.charite.de/en/>

²⁸ <https://norecopa.no/PREPARE/prepare-checklist>

initiatives, for example those aiming at device safety and efficacy demonstration using animal testing. While this approach will also be favourable with respect to the 3R principles, it might impose constraints on all subsequent steps.

TAVI - Define rationale for animal experimentation

In SIMCor, the animal experiments are not only planned to demonstrate validity of the numerical models employed for prediction of the clinical outcomes but also to assess different aspects of the device itself.

The level of details that can be provided in this public document must yet be specified.

3. Justify choice of the animal model

The choice of the animal model, i.e., the species to be used for the experiments, is a vital aspect that must be considered already during the initial planning of the experiments. As several competing interests must be considered and weighed against each other, no general recommendation can be provided. However, account should be taken of the context of use of the in-silico model for which the data are collected. Indeed, in-silico model development and credibility assessment activities require gathering data and evidence that can be more or less strictly related to the intended context of use depending on the risk associated with the model as well as the regulatory risk^{29 30}.

While the use of larger vertebrates, such as pig and sheep, seems logical due to their similar physiology, use of these species is associated with huge expenses and the strictest ethical regulations. In general, a wide variety of species might be used for cardiovascular research, ranging from small vertebrates, such as mice and rats to larger animals, such as pigs and sheep. However, if pathomechanisms, disease progression or angiogenesis are to be investigated, non-vertebrates, such as frogs³¹ and zebrafish³² might feature sufficient genetic similarity to allow translation of inferences made in these models to human physiology. There also are initiatives to provide guidance for the right choice of the animal model³³.

The focus of SIMCor, however, is the in-silico assessment of implantable cardiovascular devices. Specifically, TAVI and PAPS. These use cases already constrain the species that are viable for preclinical experiments to larger vertebrates as the cardiovascular anatomy must be of similar size to allow implantation of the devices to be tested. Additionally, hemodynamic function, as for example the cardiac output, must be comparable. However, several additional aspects must be thoroughly considered. For example, if thrombogenicity is to be investigated, the coagulation system of the animal model must be comparable to that of a human³⁴. Similarly, the bovine, porcine and ovine erythrocytes differ strongly³⁵, which must be carefully considered as those aspects might have relevant effects on aspects such as hemolysis. Finally, there are also non-academic but rather practical considerations that must be carefully considered. For example the somatic growth rate of animals might be prohibitive for chronic experiments, as the chosen animal model will deviate too strongly from human anatomy after

²⁹ Assessing the Credibility of Computational Modeling and Simulation in Medical Device Submissions. <https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/assessing-credibility-computational-modeling-and-simulation-medical-device-submissions>

³⁰ ASME V&V 40 - 2018. Assessing Credibility of Computational Modeling through Verification and Validation: Application to Medical Devices. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41684-019-0425-4>

³¹ <https://academic.oup.com/circovasres/article/91/2/279/292181>

³² <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41684-019-0425-4>

³³ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41684-019-0425-4>

³⁴ [https://www.ejves.com/article/S1078-5884\(20\)30321-X/fulltext](https://www.ejves.com/article/S1078-5884(20)30321-X/fulltext)

³⁵ <https://www.meduniwien.ac.at/hp/fileadmin/prf/windberger/ExpPhysiolfertig.pdf>

a couple months of growth. Also, animals must be kept under species appropriate conditions, which might impose further constraints. In general, extensive literature review and discussion with experts as well as the local animal research facilities is strongly advised. Usually, the choice of the animal model must be meticulously specified during the ethical approval of the animal experiments.

TAVI - Justify choice of animal model

The following reasons and consideration led to a porcine model being used for both the acute and chronic animal experiments planned in frames of SIMCor.

- As omnivores, pigs are very similar to humans regarding anatomy, physiology, digestion as well as histopathology and pharmacokinetics.
- The heart of a pig is very similar to the heart of a human regarding anatomy, shape, size and the vascular structure. Especially, sizes of the arteries are similar, which is crucial for the implantation of the PAPS.
- The physiology of the cardiovascular system is similar, meaning that pressures, flow rates and heart rates are comparable.
- The size of a pig allows testing of the sensor in its actual size, which would not be possible using smaller animals, such as mice or rats.
- The coagulation in pigs is similar compared to humans. Adhesion of platelets and general platelet activity is comparable³⁶.

4. Animal welfare considerations

Every animal experiment will be associated with a burden for the animals. According to the European guideline 2010/63/EU³⁷, article 15 this burden can be classified using the categories “non-recovery”, “mild”, “moderate” and “severe”. While designing animal experiments, measures must be considered and implemented to reduce this burden to a minimum. For example, if an experiment can be performed under general anaesthesia and the animal does not recover consciousness (i.e., the animal being euthanized after the procedure), this is considered as ‘non-recovery’. For animal experiments in which the animal is euthanized at the end, ‘non-recovery’ is considered to be the lowest level of burden. In chronic experiments which cannot be carried out under permanent general anaesthesia, the other three levels of burden must be estimated according to the above-mentioned guideline. Measures for reducing the burden are manifold and range from performing all surgeries and interventions under general anaesthesia, controlling and treating surgical wounds, administration of analgesics after the treatment to alleviate pain.

Apart from the medical management of the animals’ burden, aspects regarding how animals are kept and the animals’ hygiene must be considered. Examples for those aspects are:

- keeping animals in social environment appropriate for their species and sex
- access to food and drinking water
- cleaning, climate and lighting of stables
- measures to provide animals additional run
- measures to provide animals with occupation via special feed or toys

³⁶ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26188826/>

³⁷ Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 September 2010 on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32010L0063>

- should be regulated, and stables should be appropriate. Here, most animal research facilities have their own rules.

Here, animal research facilities usually have their own SOPs for management and regulation of these measures. These SOPs will provide valuable information for planning the animal experiments. This is not only necessary for the ethical application but also to consider the overall costs to be estimated for the animal experiments.

TAVI - Animal welfare considerations

In SIMCor the following measures are taken to enhance animal welfare and reduce their burden.

Measures to reduce or avoid pain:

- device implantation is performed under general anaesthesia and administration of Fentanyl to alleviate any pain
- animals receive additional analgesics for three days

Measures regarding Hygiene:

- animals are not washed within the first three days to allow the room; the animals are kept in to be populated by their specific germ flora
- collective faecal samples to check for parasites
- optical and olfactory examination of hay upon delivery and before usage
- daily examination of animal pens by staff and regular examination of animals by veterinarians

Conditions under which the animals are kept:

- indoor climate of ~20°C, rooms are illuminated by daylight, providing a natural day and night cycle
- animals are fed twice a day and have unlimited access to drinking water
- straw and hay are provided as additional feed and for occupation
- animals are given access to run spaces in the facility
- fruit water ice, fruits and vegetables hidden in hay or cardboard boxes are provided to increase occupation

5. Document responsibilities regarding experiments

For the approval of the animal experiments, the personnel involved in animal experiments must be disclosed: Here the specific tasks performed by each person during the animal experiments, their job description, their experience regarding animal experiments as well as required certification should be included. These aspects are regulated in articles 23 to 25 of the directive 2010/63/EU. However, the specific requirements by the local and national regulatory bodies might vary.

6. Experimental design and data storage

The experimental design must be finalised once the animal model is decided upon. Again, this might be an iterative approach, as constraints during final planning of the experimental design might require changes in previous steps, such as the animal model. Also, specific aspects of the experimental design might not be approved by the regulatory bodies, also resulting in required changes of the experimental design.

The experimental design must be planned meticulously, including all relevant steps and ideally methods for ensuring adherence to the design, such as checklists and further standard operating procedures. Opposed to in-vitro and in-silico experiments, the design of an animal experiment cannot be easily adjusted and iterated after approval. A 'learning by doing approach' is to be avoided at all

costs as it might be impossible to redo failed experiments without additional approval processes and deviation from the experimental design might also require amendment of the approval.

A relevant aspect of the experimental design is the biostatistical analysis of the required sample sizes, i.e., the number of animals required to verify or falsify the hypothesis to be investigated via the experiments. Here, the reduce-aspect of the 3R principle is to be considered. While large sample sizes will allow to already unmask smaller effects, the sample size must be as small as possible and as large as necessary. Here, no rule of thumb can be provided and this biostatistical analysis is heavily driven by the research question. However, a priori power analysis, to assess which effect size is to be demonstrated given a chosen statistical power, is a common approach. Ideally, all assumptions and data elements, as for example, estimations for the standard deviation of relevant parameters, should be justified by previous investigations or literature. Depending on the national legislation, this statistical analysis must be performed by a certified expert.

The actual investigations and procedures for data collection are too heterogenous and manifold to provide a general guideline. Depending on the model to be validated, device implantations, assessment of anatomy and device position, measurement of hemodynamic parameters as pressures and velocities, gathering of tissue samples for mechanical analyses or proteome analysis can be performed to only name a few. Naturally, the experimental design should allow acquisition of the data required for model validation while simultaneously reducing the efforts for that acquisition to a minimum. First, each and every investigation will impose an additional burden to the animal. Second, independent of this burden, acquisition procedures can be associated with severe personal, monetary and time costs. For example, while continuous assessment of imaging data for evaluation disease progression might be preferable, each image acquisition might require anaesthesia. This will not only result in an increased burden but will also drive the costs. Thus, for data acquisition, the question ‘how good is good enough’ should be always kept in mind. Especially for validation of in-silico models, the standard V&V:40³⁸ on “*Assessing Credibility of Computational Modeling through Verification and Validation: Application to Medical Devices*” should be considered for guidance on the identification of relevant quantities of interest, their required accuracy and the means for their assessment.

Finally, not only the process regarding the animal experiments directly, but also all related procedures should be planned and tested before the first actual experiments. These include testing of all measurement techniques to be applied during the experiments, their export capabilities and how to store the data and samples. For example, image data might be stored in clinical picture archiving and communication systems. However, depending on the model, access to the raw data generated by the scanner might be required.

When reporting computational results in a regulatory process, regulators may require the ‘certificate of birth’ of the experimental data used to build and/or validate the model. Keeping track of each step transparently will contribute to demonstrating the model credibility, which can be aided by following a data management plan. Indeed, a DMP can help establish a set of rules and processes for handling of the research data during and after the end of the project, establishing what data will be collected, processed and/or generated, which methodology & standards will be applied, whether data will be shared/made open access, and how data will be curated & preserved (including after the end of the

³⁸ <https://www.asme.org/codes-standards/find-codes-standards/v-v-40-assessing-credibility-computational-modeling-verification-validation-application-medical-devices>

project). DMP templates are provided for example by the EU Commission for Horizon 2020 projects, if helpful³⁹.

Contingencies

If the researcher cannot adhere to the content of these SOP instructions for justified reasons, then deviation from the procedure must be documented and appropriate actions must be taken, considering SOP revision if relevant.

Publication policy

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- <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory/research-development/scientific-guidelines/non-clinical/non-clinical-development>
- PREPARE guidelines (Planning Research and Experimental Procedures on Animals: Recommendations for Excellence): <https://norecopa.no/PREPARE/prepare-checklist>.

³⁹ Data Management Plan example: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm